

Studies in Diphenyl Series. Part III. A New Route to Phenanthrene.

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9-Hydroxyphenanthrene has been synthesised from a diphenyl derivative and this method seems to be more general for the synthesis of phenanthrenes than the method outlined in a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 418).

Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (I) is condensed with ethyl chloroacetate and the diethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (II), thus obtained, is hydrolysed to yield cyclohexanone-2-acetic acid (III). After esterification it is treated with phenyl magnesium bromide and the ethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate (IV), thus obtained, is dehydrogenated by means of sulphur when ethyl diphenyl-2-acetate (V) is obtained. Ethyl diphenyl-2-acetate after hydrolysis is treated with sulphuric acid when 9-hydroxy-phenanthrene (VI) is obtained. Phenanthrene can be obtained from it by heating with selenium.

Ethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate gives the corresponding acid on hydrolysis. The compound (II), when submitted to Grignard's reaction, gives a lactone (VII) which on hydrolysis with caustic potash gives the lactonic acid (VIII).

This lactone may also be utilised for the synthesis of phenanthrene. Further work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (II).—Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (25 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (3.4 g.) in alcohol (31 c.c.) and the solid sodium salt was heated under reflux for 6 hours with ethyl chloroacetate (19 g.). After dilution the condensation product was extracted with ether, the ether removed and the product distilled at 168°-175°/11 mm; yield 18 g. (Found: C, 60.6; H, 7.7. C₁₃H₂₀O₅ requires C, 60.9; H, 7.8 per cent).

cycloHexanone-2-acetic acid (III).—Diethyl cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (20 g.) was boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 vol.) for 7 hours. After removal of the mineral acid under reduced pressure, cyclohexanone-2-acetic acid was distilled at 163°/4 mm. (Found: C, 61.2; H, 7.5. C₈H₁₂O₃ requires C, 61.5; H, 7.6 per cent).

Ethyl cyclohexanone-2-acetate was obtained by esterifying cyclohexanone-2-acetic acid with 3 parts of alcohol saturated at 0° with hydrochloric acid at room temperature and keeping overnight. It was isolated as usual and distilled at 122°/5 mm. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 8.5. C₁₀H₁₆O₃ requires C, 65.1; H, 8.6 per cent). The *semicarba-*

zone crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 196-97°. (Found: N, 17.8. $C_{11}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires N, 17.4 per cent).

Ethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate (IV).—Phenyl magnesium bromide (from 2.3 c.c. of bromobenzene and 0.82 g. of magnesium) was added drop by drop to a cooled ethereal solution of *cyclohexanone-2-acetate* (4 g.) and the mixture left overnight. The product was decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid, the ether removed and it was distilled at 170-180°/8 mm. (Found: C, 73.0; H, 8.1. $C_{16}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 73.2; H, 8.3 per cent).

1-Hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetic acid was obtained on refluxing ethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate with alcoholic potash for 2 hours. The alcohol was distilled off and after dilution the unchanged ester was removed by ether. The aqueous layer was concentrated and after acidification the free acid was extracted with ether, the ether removed, the product kept in a vacuum desiccator for 2 days when it solidified. It was finally crystallised from water, m.p. 129°. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 7.5. $C_{14}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 71.8; H, 7.6 per cent).

Diethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate-2-carboxylate and its lactone (VII).—When an ethereal solution of diethyl *cyclohexanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate* was treated with phenyl magnesium bromide a gelatinous precipitate separated. The mixture was left overnight and decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with ether, the product collecting at 180°-190°/9 mm. was found to be a liquid while that coming between 190°-220°/9 mm. was found to solidify, at the laboratory temperature. From the second fraction, the solid was obtained in a pure form by crystallising from alcohol, m.p. 97°, and it was found to be the lactone of diethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate-2-carboxylate. (Found: C, 70.9; H, 6.9. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 70.8; H, 6.9 per cent).

It is possible to convert the liquid (b.p. 180-190°/9 mm.), which is diethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate-2-carboxylate into the solid, by leaving it in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 for several days. (Found: C, 68.4; H, 7.9. $C_{19}H_{26}O_5$ requires C, 68.2; H, 7.7 per cent).

The lactone of *1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-carboxy-2-acetic acid* (VIII) was obtained by hydrolysing the ester by refluxing with alcoholic potash for 3 hours. After removing the alcohol it was diluted and the ester removed by ether. The aqueous layer was concentrated, acidified and extracted with ether, the ether removed

and the product was kept in a desiccator for 2 days when it solidified. It was crystallised from water, m.p. 141°. (Found: C, 69.0; H, 6.0. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.1 per cent).

Ethyl diphenyl-2-acetate (V).—Ethyl 1-hydroxyhexahydrodiphenyl-2-acetate was dehydrogenated by means of sulphur and the product after washing with caustic alkali was distilled at 165-175°/8 mm. (Found: C, 79.7; H, 6.2. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 6.6 per cent).

9-Hydroxyphenanthrene (VI).—Ethyl diphenyl-2-acetate was hydrolysed by means of alcoholic potash and the product was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid on the water-bath for some time. After dilution it was distilled in vacuum and the portion coming between 220-260°/12 mm. was dissolved in alcohol, and a saturated solution of picric acid added, when a red-coloured picrate was precipitated. It was filtered, washed and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 185°. 9-Hydroxyphenanthrene, regenerated from the pure picrate, melts at 153°.

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